

Research Article

A Review of Cybersecurity Awareness Focusing on Software and Email Security

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Abstract: *This paper describes the literature related to cybersecurity awareness with specific reference to software security and email security in general. The aim of the paper is to collect information from previous research on cybersecurity awareness with special reference to software security and email security in general. The authors applied the method of non-systematic review of articles from few online databases in order to collect information related to the topics mentioned above. Through a non-systematic literature review on cybersecurity awareness that focuses on software and email security, this is considered as an attempt to educate everyone about the need for cybersecurity awareness. Cybersecurity awareness is necessary for people, businesses, and organisations to securely navigate the digital domain. Cybersecurity and software security work mutually beneficial when it comes to protecting computer systems and data from harmful actions. Email security is a vital component of cybersecurity since email is still one of the most commonly used communication methods for both individuals and businesses. It was found from the literature review that the cybersecurity awareness either regarding email security or software security is very important for the organisations and individuals, so that they will take all kinds of precautions and measures to remain secured and protected from the cyber threats.*

Keywords: *cybersecurity; software security; email security; cybersecurity awareness.*

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Internet is a global network of computers that allows individuals to connect and exchange information in real time. There is a lot of material available on the internet in almost every field. Direct engagement, business transactions, and leisure activities such as internet surfing, advertising campaigns, financial transactions, and Internet shopping are examples of Internet applications. With all of the advantages that the Internet provides, it is also responsible for security and privacy issues. The internet is the source of all publicly available information that is exploited, such as through visiting new websites, engaging in Internet fraud, and unwittingly providing information to third parties. The validity of the path by which the information is conveyed is under doubt.

Spamming and phishing are serious network security issues because they attempt to steal money and personal information. Everyone with an Internet connection has a significant impact on a company's cyber security. An institution's Internet security is the sum of all vulnerable security breaches caused by personnel habits and vulnerabilities. A corporation's human attack surface comprises negligence, mistakes, disease, mortality, insider threats, and media manipulation risks. Spyware is a popular and successful social manipulation technique that takes advantage of the human attack surface.

Therefore, cybersecurity awareness, or information security awareness, has become an important issue today. Cybercriminals continuously develop new strategies to exploit weaknesses and obtain unauthorised access to sensitive information, making cybersecurity knowledge critical in protecting against cyber threats. Individuals and organisations may better recognise and respond to possible threats by increasing cybersecurity knowledge, lowering the probability of being a victim of a cyberattack.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides the literature review on cybersecurity awareness, software security and email security; Section 4 discussion; and Section 5 is the conclusion section and references.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Cybersecurity Awareness

Cybersecurity is defined as the component of information security that focuses primarily on preserving the confidentiality, integrity, and availability (CIA) of digital information assets against dangers that may develop as a result of such assets being compromised via (using) the internet (Von Solms, B.,2018). It was also said that the term "cybersecurity" has a broad definition (ISO, 2018) and cyber security may help with risk management and prevent cyber attacks and data breaches. Security assaults, which come in two varieties (active and passive attacks), and security objectives are among the features of security that are defined by the security architecture (Stallings, 2006). The definition of cybersecurity according to ITU-T (2008) is "the collection of things, consisting of security concepts, policies, tools, guidelines, security safeguards, actions, risk management methods, training, technologies, assurance and best practises, which can be applied to protect users' assets as well as the organisation and cyber environment".

In academic writing, the phrase "cybersecurity awareness" is referred to as "information security" (Vazquez, 2019). A successful programme would be created and effective tactics would be chosen for the intended audience with the help of an overview of users' present level of awareness and perceptions. In addition to offering training programmes for users or employees, cybersecurity awareness raises users' or workers' knowledge of cybersecurity in an organisation and teaches them how to recognise threats to or assaults from it (Nachin et al., 2019; NIST, 2011). Hwang et al.(2021) described information security awareness as a phenomenon that tries to assist users in noticing the security vulnerabilities or problems that may develop and responding in an appropriate way. Naturally, it also seeks to keep the security phenomena on the internet at the forefront of the user's thoughts. Hwang's remarks were echoed by Khan et al.(2015) who defined information security awareness as people having knowledge about security and acting within the scope of recognised regulations.

Typically, security awareness is evaluated in the first phases of software development. A reference model of awareness-related needs is thought to determine the functional scale of security awareness programmes, according to a number of studies. These programmes generally work to increase users' knowledge of the most common cyberthreats, the laws and policies of their nation and institution, and the procedures that must be adhered to in order to secure their digital assets (Hansche, 2001; Maqousi et al., 2014; Sabillon et al., 2019). The frequency and severity of cyberattacks have increased due to the lack of internet information about cybercrime and the high degree of concern. During the pandemic, a number of cyberattacks were recorded against healthcare providers, government agencies, support platforms, efforts to advertise COVID-19 remedies fraudulently, and more (Lallie et al., 2020; Pranggono and Arabo, 2021).

In cybersecurity awareness, a number of variables are present, including human factors. Age, gender, education, university credentials, and IT experience are some of these determinants (Bordonaba-Juste et al., 2020; Jeong et al., 2019; Li et al., 2020). According to Daengsi (et al., 2021) simulations of security risk scenarios, cybersecurity drills, and awareness training should all be included in a strategy. A plan should be employed as a component of the organization's cybersecurity awareness programme in order to increase employee cybersecurity awareness. Such a tailored programme might be used as a tool to inform, teach, and raise awareness among staff members or users in each organisation on how to defend themselves and their companies against cyberattacks.

As the Internet has expanded, individuals' lives are becoming more affected by cyberthreats (such as the disclosure of personal information). According to Yeom (et al., 2020) most security systems are weak because users do not understand how to use the technology, which leads to frequent information leaks by insiders. According to Tom Olzak (2006) a security awareness programme that focuses on the realisation aspect and active participation of the people involved in the software development and usage process for maintenance on three fronts confidentiality, integrity, and secure availability of the information with the aim of creating a fully aware workforce.

According to Mohammed A. Alqahtani (2022), all actions carried out online facilitate many activities, but adversely, they open themselves to cyberattacks that might reveal user data and information to unauthorised parties. With the help of cyber security awareness, users may be taught about the dangers that lie online, how to avoid them, and what to do in the case of a security crisis. Additionally, it fosters in them a proactive feeling of obligation to protect the privacy of others. For it to be most useful and successful, users' awareness of cyber security must be a widespread endeavour. John Steven, Ken van Wyk (2006) proposed that the development team, security team, and operational team should be trained in order to raise awareness among them. Programmes for cybersecurity education and awareness may contribute to national security and should be well-organized to provide individuals a foundational understanding of the subject (Al-Janabi, S.; Al-Shourbaji ; 2016).

2.2 Software Security

Saikath Bhattacharya, Munindar P. Singh, and Laurie Williams (2021) claim that software security is a major issue since software flaws might result in cyber-attacks, breach user privacy, or result in financial loss. The President's executive order on criteria to assess software security was motivated by recent supply chain breaches, including the Solar Winds cyber-attack. Businesses must evaluate the security of their products before releasing them in order to reduce cyber-attacks. Based on operational performance indicators, software businesses track software test data and determine the programme's readiness for release. Software releases, however, depend on a variety of factors, including software

providers, stakeholders, and client business requirements. An early or late release might have a detrimental impact on the product's performance overall, return on investment, consumer happiness, and manufacturing costs. By extrapolating the decrease in vulnerabilities during testing, software security growth charts the growth in software security. Software security preparedness determines the ideal release window by taking security growth into account. Companies frequently use specialised software security testing tools and dedicate extra testing time to analyse software security, delaying the delivery of software as a result. It might be difficult for management, software testers, and developers to provide a secure software release on schedule.

According to McAfee (2017) on a computer or mobile device, software or applications must be updated. Software updates are essential because they typically contain crucial security fixes. Skipping software updates puts you at danger of identity theft, financial loss, and other problems since it gives hackers access to your personal information. Software upgrades may provide new or better capabilities, as well as increased compatibility with other hardware or software, in addition to security patches.) They can also increase the stability of your programme by deleting outdated features.

The amount of services offered on the Internet is growing, argues Atsuo Hazeyama and Hiroto Shimizu (2012). The proliferation of mobile terminals or data electronics in the near future will ensure the continuation of this trend. Computer security is becoming more crucial along with this development. In recent years, as more and more services have been implemented using software and as software complexity has increased, it has become clear how important software security technologies are in addition to network security technologies like encryption or access control. Software security is concerned with security across the whole software development process, which means it goes beyond merely integrating network security technologies into software systems to include a variety of security-related tasks. According to Mano Paul, the right technology should be chosen, the process should be hack-resistant, and the people should be made aware, educated, and informed appropriately in order to create safe software.

Malicious software programmes called internet threats are intended to target consumers when they use the internet and Internet browsers account for 61% of the vulnerabilities utilised in cybercrime assaults against home users, according to the kind of attacking application software (Kaspersky Lab, 2015a).

According to Benbasat and Moore (1991) because the internet may be a dangerous and unsettling environment, cautious security software selection is crucial for online protection. This calls for research into how factors including relative advantage, compatibility, usability, visibility, voluntariness, image, probability of results, and testability affect the likelihood that people would use internet security software.

2.3 Email Security

According to McAfee (2017) email may be used to communicate with people, obtain information, and submit applications for employment, internships, and scholarships, among other things. Depending on the user's objectives, the formality, target audience, and intended effect of the message the user delivers will vary. Email is typically used to convey spam, malware, and phishing assaults from unidentified senders. Therefore that data and information may be safeguarded, it is crucial to understand email security.

Email security is the process of defending against email risks in order to ensure the availability, integrity, and authenticity of email communications. Email allows billions of people and organisations to send messages to one another. Email is central to how people use the internet, and it has long been a target for hackers (Kerner, S. M. 2022). Online identity theft has a kind known as phishing. To

(thousands of) potential victims, it is typically carried out by sending emails (Ayodele et al., 2012, p. 208). Phishing is one type of dangerous cyber-attack in this day and age. In these attacks, phishers typically employ phoney email accounts and/or phoney websites to attempt to obtain users' login information (Chaudhry et al., 2016).

Phishing attacks are defined as criminal actions utilising both technological and social engineering approaches (Aleroud & Zhou, 2017; Bahnsen et al., 2017; Peng et al., 2018). Phishing may be simple to avoid, but developments in the phishing community are making phishing schemes harder for victims to spot (Vayansky & Kumar, 2018).

Phishing is a sort of social engineering in which attackers try to fraudulently get sensitive information from the victim by posing as a reliable third party, according to the study on "Social Phishing" (Jagatic et al., 2005). Phishing assaults are unquestionably a common tactic used by online fraudsters. It is argued that part of the blame for why phishing attacks are so successful could be shifted towards email clients. Therefore, email clients should use a reliable and secure protection method to safeguard email users in this way (Mohammed A. Alqahtani, 2022).

Anyone with an email address might be the victim of phishing. Due to the wide distribution of phishing emails, it can be inferred that the majority of email users may become a target of such attacks. However, in order to effectively prevent phishing attempts, users must also be aware of these assaults, and the onus of spotting them should not just fall on the software side. The email client software should thus be built and developed in such a way that it "educates" the users. Furnell (2005, p. 276) asserts that the programme should always "provide a visible indication of the security status" because this is one of the main reasons why users are uneasy about the security of their software.

According to Luga (et al., 2016) phishing is a technique used by attackers to trick users into divulging sensitive information. This type of cyber-attack or threat aims to trick victims into disclosing sensitive information in order to steal money from them or install malware on their devices, such as usernames, passwords, and financial information (Bahnsen et al., 2017; Chaudhry et al., 2016; Peng et al., 2018).

According to Jagatic (et al., 2005) The closing inquiry, "Do you know the sender of the email?" can be called into question to some extent because phishing emails rarely impersonate a person. Remember that phishing is a type of social engineering in which an attacker tries to obtain sensitive information from a victim fraudulently by pretending to be a reliable third party.

According to Furnell (2005, pp. 274-279) titled "Why consumers should not use security," said "some obvious awareness issues remain to be overcome, and unfortunately there is sufficient evidence to show that consumers do not actually understand security well in the first place." With that, in order for their phishing attacks to be successful, phishers use vulnerabilities in email clients. To reduce phishing attacks, these vulnerabilities must be addressed. The failure of the software (email client) to identify the email as a phishing attack and the user's belief in the email being authentic is what leads to the success of the phishing attack.

3. DISCUSSION

The study's findings indicate that there is a lot of information available on security awareness, including information about software security and email security, which really present a lot of potential for crime if users do not pay attention to it. In today's digital world, cybersecurity knowledge is fundamental. Individuals, businesses, and organisations must be aware of the possible dangers and hazards that exist online as their reliance on technology and the internet grows. Education is a critical component in increasing cybersecurity awareness. Cyber dangers such as phishing, malware,

ransomware, and social engineering must be educated on. They should be informed of how these threats may affect them and the consequences of succumbing to them.

Individuals who are aware of these risks can take the necessary precautions to safeguard their personal information and digital assets. Adopting claimed safe browsing practices is another critical component of cybersecurity knowledge. Security precautions include using strong and unique passwords for different accounts, enabling two-factor authentication, keeping software and operating systems up to date, and exercising care when clicking on links or downloading files from unfamiliar sources. Backing up data on a regular basis is also essential since it may help reduce the damage of a prospective cyberattack.

Organisations also play an important role in raising cybersecurity awareness. They should provide extensive staff training programmes to ensure that everyone understands the importance of cybersecurity and how to recognise and respond to possible attacks. Establishing clear policies and practices for managing sensitive information, as well as performing regular security audits, may also help foster a cybersecurity culture inside an organisation. Government and regulatory entities are also responsible for raising cybersecurity awareness. To safeguard individuals and organisations from cyber risks, they might organise public campaigns, develop cybersecurity rules and standards, and enforce legislation. Governments may cooperate to create a safer digital environment for everyone by encouraging collaboration between the public and commercial sectors.

Cybersecurity awareness is also vital for individuals, businesses, and organizations to traverse the digital realm safely. By educating ourselves, adopting best practices, and being attentive, we can limit the dangers of cyberattacks and secure our digital life. It is a continuing activity that demands continuous learning and adaptation to keep one step ahead of the ever-evolving cyber Hence, cybersecurity and software security work mutually beneficial when it comes to protecting computer systems and data from harmful actions.

Software security refers to the procedures used during the software development process to guarantee that software programmes are resistant to assaults and vulnerabilities. There is relevance of software security in the field of cybersecurity. Software security has become essential because many cyberattacks target flaws in software programmes. These vulnerabilities might be unintended code mistakes, design faults, or poor security measures. Attackers routinely hunt for these flaws to obtain illegal access, steal sensitive information, or disrupt the functioning of software systems. There are certain crucial factors to consider while discussing software security, such as secure development practices. Adopting safe coding methods is vital to limiting vulnerabilities in software systems. Developers should follow secure coding rules and frameworks, undertake thorough testing, and conduct code reviews to discover and address any security problems before delivering the product. Then, regular updates and patching: Software manufacturers should routinely deliver updates and fixes to address reported vulnerabilities. It is vital for consumers to keep their software apps UpToDate to guarantee they have the latest security updates. Validating and sanitising user input is critical for preventing attacks such as SQL injection, cross-site scripting (XSS), and command injection.

Software developers can reduce the danger of these sorts of attacks by ensuring that user input is properly handled and sanitised. Authentication and authorization, proper authentication and authorization procedures must be implemented to prevent unauthorized access to software systems. Effective security methods include strong password restrictions, multi-factor authentication, and role-

based access controls. Thereafter, security awareness and training. Promoting security awareness among software developers and users is vital. Training programmes may educate employees on common security risks, recommended practices, and the need to maintain software security throughout the development and deployment lifecycle. By emphasising software security, firms may drastically lower the risk of cyberattacks and data breaches. It's crucial to include security measures in the software development process from the very beginning and regularly monitor and upgrade software programmes to keep ahead of emerging risks.

Apart from that, email security is an important area of cybersecurity because email is still one of the most regularly utilised communication channels for both individuals and enterprises. It is critical to protect email accounts and the information contained inside them to avoid unauthorized access, data breaches, phishing attempts, and other email-related dangers. Let us go through some crucial concerns for email security. Firstly, strong passwords. Using secure, unique passwords for email accounts is vital. Passwords should be complicated, having a combination of uppercase and lowercase letters, numbers, and special characters. It's vital to avoid using easily guessable information such as birthdays or frequent phrases. Additionally, activating two-factor authentication (2FA) adds an extra layer of protection by requiring a second form of verification, such as a code texted to a mobile device. Secondly, encryption: encrypting email exchanges guarantees that the content of emails stays private and safe. Secure methods such as Transport Layer Security (TLS) encrypt the connection between mail servers, whereas end-to-end encryption encrypts the email message itself. End-to-end encryption ensures that only the intended receiver can decrypt and read the communication, offering a higher level of security.

Phishing assaults are a frequent approach used by attackers to deceive users into providing sensitive information. It is crucial to be cautious when clicking on links or opening attachments in emails, especially from unfamiliar or dubious sources. Verify the validity of the email and sender before submitting any sensitive information or interacting with the material. Keep in mind that email security is a joint responsibility of service providers, people, and businesses. By putting these precautions in place and remaining watchful, you can greatly improve the security of your email conversations and keep critical information from getting into the wrong hands.

4. CONCLUSION

This review describes the literature related to cybersecurity awareness with specific reference to software security and email security in general. Cyber awareness based on both software and email security is vital in today's digital world. As for software security, regular updates, safe coding techniques, and vulnerability assessments are crucial to defending against potential attacks and fixing flaws. Secure deployment, setup, and integration of security into the software development lifecycle (SDLC) further increases software security. Moreover, for email security, the knowledge of users plays a significant role in combating email-based attacks such as phishing. Educating consumers about spotting malicious emails, avoiding clicking unfamiliar links or downloading attachments, and using email filtering and encryption technologies are crucial to lowering risk. Thus, by emphasising cyber awareness in both software and email security, firms may strengthen their cybersecurity posture, lower the risk of cyber attacks, and secure critical information. Ongoing training, user education, and coordination between IT professionals and end users are vital to establishing a successful cyber protection plan.

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